

CHEMICAL CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIMICROBIAL PROPERTIES OF CARICA PAPAYA LEAF EXTRACT: A MULTI-ASSAY APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

Carica papaya, a widely cultivated fruit crop in tropical and subtropical regions, has been the subject of extensive research owing to its potential therapeutic properties. This study investigated the phytochemical composition and evaluated the cytotoxic, toxicological, and antibacterial activities of *Carica papaya* leaf extract. Fresh leaves were collected, washed, and subjected to percolation extraction using ethanol as solvent. (TLC) screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, anthraquinones, anthrones, essential oils, fatty acids, flavonoids, phenols, steroids, and tannins. The cytotoxicity of the extracts was assessed using the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (BSLA), which demonstrated significant cytotoxic effects with a 100% mortality rate after 48 h and an LC₅₀ of -68977.14 ppm after 24 h. The *Allium cepa* test further confirmed the cytotoxic potential of the extracts, affecting cell division and resulting in a low mitotic index of 23.14 at 2000 ppm concentration. Antibacterial activity of the extracts was evaluated using the Kirby-Bauer Assay against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The results showed notable antibacterial activity, with mean zones of inhibition of 14.28 mm and 17.65 mm, respectively, indicating the potential of *Carica papaya* leaf extracts as natural antimicrobial agents. This comprehensive study highlights the rich bioactive composition and significant biological activities of *Carica papaya* leaves, supporting their potential for therapeutic applications and warranting further research on their medicinal properties.

Keywords: *Allium Cepa Test, Antibacterial Activity, BSLA, Cytotoxicity, Kirby-Bauer Assay, Phytochemicals, Thin-Layer Chromatography*

INTRODUCTION

Papaya is a fruit crop widely grown in tropical and subtropical regions. Papaya is a semi-woody tropical herb that proliferates quickly (Silva et al., 2007). It is a member of the Caricaceae family, so the term "Carica" is used as a suffix to its scientific name, *Carica papaya*. Although it can be grown elsewhere, its native habitat is in the United States (Vedantu, n.d.). Papayas are typically cultivated from seeds. Papaya seeds are categorized as having intermediate resistance to desiccation, unlike the seeds of many tropical species, which are neither recalcitrant nor dormant (Silva et al., 2007). This fruit-bearing plant seed is easier to handle and store than other tropical seeds are.

The selected specimen for this study consisted of *Carica papaya* leaves collected from a papaya tree growing in a local garden in Quirino, Naguilian, Isabela. The location where the specimen was obtained was warm, well-drained, and stricken by abundant sunlight and fertile soil. *Carica papaya* leaves are arranged spirally in a terminal cluster, differing in size and along global borders. Their rounded forms, long petioles, and alternate arrangements define them. In addition, the bundle of leaves has an intense, dark green to yellow-green color, with a diameter of 60-90 cm, and every leaf has a lifespan of four–six months (Wadekar et al., 2021).

The Philippines planted papaya on 8,647.41 hectares of land in 2011; the total amount of papaya produced was 157,906.79 MT (Yebeles, 2015), and the typical lifespan ranges from to 3-5 years (Dmcoffee, 2024). The availability and long lifespan of papaya plants are good indicators of their biological use. Papaya leaves are rich in flavonoids, alkaloids, tannins, saponins, and glycosides. (Wadekar et al., 2021). Considering the phytochemical makeup, pharmacological characteristics, and outcomes of several preclinical and clinical investigations, papaya leaves have been found to be effective in treating epidemics. Reviews showed that Papaya leaf extracts can be used successfully in clinical settings as an additional herbal treatment in the healthcare system (Sharma et al., 2022). According to Ingente and Anselmo (2024), ability underscores the wide-ranging utility of plant species in addressing both health and environmental concerns. Similarly, *Carica papaya* possesses significant bioactive properties, including antimicrobial activities, which have been the focus of numerous studies due to their potential therapeutic applications. While *Ipomoea reptans* is recognized for its environmental cleansing role, *Carica papaya* may play a crucial role in antimicrobial therapy, expanding the use of plant-based approaches in various domain

Overall, the researcher has chosen *Carica papaya* as a specimen because of the following conditions and characteristics: the availability of the study area, quick growth, long lifespan, and bioactive components that were proven in other studies. The study by Anselmo et al. (2024), which highlighted the durability of *Lakatan* pseudo-stem through its chemical properties contributing the chemical characterization of *Carica papaya* leaf extract in this research, further emphasizing the sustainable potential of natural resources for various industrial applications. In this study, the bioactive elements of *Papaya carica* were examined in detail. Specifically, we will apply the percolation method to extract compounds and perform a thorough toxicological evaluation. Utilizing this two-pronged strategy, we can assess the safety of papaya for use in various applications and better appreciate its potential therapeutic benefits.

Research Questions

1. What is the phytochemical composition of *Carica papaya* leaf extract?
2. What are its cytotoxic properties, assessed by Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay and *Allium cepa* test?
3. What are its toxicological effects of *carica papaya* leaf extract?
4. What is its antibacterial activity *carica papaya* leaf extract against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*?

METHODOLOGY

1. Collection and Extraction of *Carica papaya* Leaves

Fresh leaves of *Carica papaya* were meticulously gathered from a local garden in Quirino, Naguilian, Isabela, and then subjected to preliminary washing to remove surface impurities. Percolation and water bathing were utilized as extraction methods. Percolation extraction provides a basic method for extracting constituents from a particular specimen. The equipment and operation were simple and easy to conduct. It is also known for its applications in medicinal materials. Considering that heat is not required to extract the necessary constituents from the sample, this would be a great choice, especially for acquiring unstable constituents under thermal conditions (Wang et al., 2020). Ethanol was used as the solvent. Ethanol is one of the primary extractants of tannins, which are made up of polymeric phenols that have antibacterial, anthelmintic, and antidiarrheal properties, such as ellagitannin (Nortjie et al., 2022). The water bath method is another technique used to remove excess solvents from the extract. A water bath is common laboratory equipment used to maintain a constant temperature during various chemical processes. Moreover, this technique provides gentle and controlled heating, which allows the solvent to evaporate slowly. As the solvent evaporated, the remaining material became more concentrated, resulting in a semi-solid or solid extract (Arangusti, 2019). The crude extract of the papaya leaves obtained through percolation is green in color, has low viscosity, and a herbaceous and pungent odor, which may indicate a bitter taste.

2. Thin Layer Chromatography Screening Test

The table provides the following procedure to determine the different bioactives present in *Carica papaya*

REAGENT	COMPOUND TESTED	PROCEDURE AND INDICATOR OF POSITIVE RESULT
1. Preliminary Test	Essential Oils	Heat at 90 °C; violet spot under UV 365 nm
2. Vanillin Sulfuric Acid	Higher Alcohols, Steroids, Triterpenes,	-Heat at 90 °C (Char)

	Essential Oils, Phenols, Fatty Acid	- Triterpenes and sterols appear mainly as blue violet spots under long wave UV 365 nm - Essential oils from zones with wide range of colors under longwave Uv 365 nm - Phenols appear as brown spot under visible light -Fatty Acids as yellow spot under visible light
3. @ Naphthol-sulfuric Acid	Sugars	-Heat at 90 °C (char) - Blue dark spot under visible light
4. Metanolic potassium hydroxide (KOH-MetOH)	Antraquinones, Coumarins, Anthrones	- Anthraquinones give orange coloration under visible light -Coumarines react to form blue colored zone under longwave UV 326 nm - Anthrones give yellow zones under longwave UV 326 nm
5. Potassium Ferricyanide-ferric chloride	Tannins, Flavonoids, Phenols	Blue Spots under visible light
6. Dragendorff's Reagent	Alkaloids	Brown-orange visible spots IMMEDIATELY upon immersing into test reagent; colors are not stable
7. Antimony (III) Chloride	Flavonoids, Steroids	Intense Yellow to orange upon immersing for glycosidic flavonoids; fluorescent colors under longwave UV365 nm for steroids
8. Magnesium Acetate	Anthraquinones	-Heat at 90 °C (Char) - orange-violet color after heating
9. Ninhydrin	Amino Acids	Violet upon dipping

3. Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (Cytotoxicity Assay)

Preparation of seawater and Brine shrimp

The CNS Laboratory assistants provided brine shrimp, used as test organisms, and artificial seawater for the preparation of the stock solution.

Preparation of test solution

An analytical balance was used to weigh 30 mg of the plant extract. A stock solution was prepared by dissolving 30 mg of the plant extract in 15 mL of artificial seawater. An ELISA microplate with four replicates was set up and labeled as A-D (columns) and 1-6 (rows). Artificial seawater (1 mL) was added to each test tube, except for A1–D1, which contained 2000 PPM stock solution. Following this, a two-fold serial

dilution using 1 mL of the stock solution for each replicate was performed, starting from A2 to D2 replicates.

Each test tube, including A1-D1, contained ten nauplii (see Fig. 2). Dead nauplii were counted after 24–48 h.

Calculation

Two formulas were used to calculate the stock solution and the percentage of death of Brine Shrimp.

- a. Calculation for the stock solution

$$PPM = \frac{g \text{ solute}}{g \text{ solution}} \times 10^6$$

- b. Calculation of Percent for Death of *Artemia salina* (Brine shrimp)

$$\% \text{ of Death} = \frac{\text{Number of dead nauplii}}{\text{Number of dead nauplii} + \text{Number of live nauplii}} \times 100$$

4. *Allium cepa* Test

Preparation of solution

To prepare the solution, 2 mg of the crude extract was weighed on an analytical scale and diluted in 1 liter of distilled water. Following this, two-fold serial dilutions were performed to achieve 2000, 1000, 500, 250, and 125 ppm concentrations.

Cultivation of Allium cepa

Onion root tips were prepared by initiating the growth phase using small glasses and plastic cups. To ensure the harvest of root tips, two set-ups, set-A (see Fig.1) and set-B (see Fig.2), each consisting of six onions, including one control, were established. After four days, onions with root tips ranging from 0.5 to 1 cm in length were observed, and treatment with serially diluted concentrations was performed on five selected onions (see Fig. 3). The onion crops were exposed to varying concentrations for 48 h. After exposure, the onion root tips were cut to 1 cm length and immediately fixed between 12:30 and 1:00 midnight. The cut tips were preserved and securely placed in small glass vials containing 1 mL Carnoy's fluid.

Preparation of slide for observation

The primary step was to prepare all the laboratory tools and equipment, including petri dishes, scalpel knives, slides, cover slips, and microscopes. Masks and gloves were used as safety precautions. Moreover, some chemicals and reagents required for the staining procedure must be included prior to working in the laboratory. These are the 1NaCl, acetocarmine, and safranin.

The first step during laboratory activity is the hydrolysis of onion root tips, wherein root tips are placed in petridish with 1NaCl for 10 min. After 10 min, the tip was dipped in water for a few seconds and transferred to a Petri dish with acetocarmine for 5-10 minutes. Afterward, the root tips were dipped in distilled water for a few seconds to wash excess reagents and placed on the slide. Then, cover it with the coverslip and slightly squash it using the pencil, ensuring that there is not too much pressure on it. The slide was then incorporated into the compound microscope to observe mitotic activity under HPO and LPO. A cell phone was used to document the observation underneath the lenses.

The Mitotic Index was computed using the following formula:

$$MI = \frac{\text{Number of cells undergoing mitosis}}{\text{Total number of cells}} \times 100$$

5. Antibacterial Test (Bioassay)

This bioassay incorporated Disc Diffusion or Kirby-Bauer Assay to evaluate the antibiotic effectiveness of *Carica papaya* leaf crude extract against bacteria, comparing it to positive and negative controls.

Preparation of Media and Bacterial Broth

The SMU Center for Natural Sciences (CNS) laboratory assistant prepared the medium and bacterial cultures. The press contained a blend of meat and tryptone soy agar in distilled water. *Escherichia coli* and *S. aureus* were cultured in separate broths.

Culture Plate Inoculation

First, the outside of a petri dish containing solidified agar was labeled. The bacterial broth in the test tube was mixed, its cap was removed, and the cap and tube were flame-sterilized. A sterile cotton swab was then dipped into the tube, flame-sterilized, and recapped. After holding the Petri dish, the swab spread the bacteria across the agar in a side-to-side pattern, ensuring at least three rotations for uniform distribution. Dispose of swabs after use in a biohazard container. Four Petri dishes were prepared for *E. coli* and three for *S. Aureus*.

Sample Preparation, Placement, and Incubation

filter paper discs were immersed in the crude extract overnight. The forceps were sterilized and used to place the soaked filter paper discs onto the culture plates according to their labels. Positive controls were positioned away from the discs. ten (10) ug of meropenem (MeM) were used for the four *E. Coli* plates, and clindamycin was used for the three *S. Aureus* plates. Ethanol-soaked discs served as negative controls. After sealing the culture plates with bond paper, the plates were incubated at 35°C for 24 h.

Post-incubation

The inhibition zones around the paper discs were measured using a digital caliper and their diameters were compared to those around the positive control discs on each plate.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thin Layer Chromatographic Screening Test

Table 1. Phytochemical Constituents of the *C. papaya*

Phytochemical Components	Result
Alkaloids	+
Amino Acids	-
Anthraquinones	+
Anthrone	+
Anthraquinones	+
Coumarins	-
Essential Oils	+
Fatty Acid	+
Flavonoids, Tannins, and Phenols	+
Higher Alcohols	-
Steroids	+
Sugars	-
Triterpenes	-

Legend:

(+) Positive/ Present

(-) Negative/ Absent

C. papaya contains alkaloids, anthraquinones, anthrones, essential oils, fatty acids, flavonoids, phenols, steroids, and tannins.

Some alkaloids, such as nicotine, are used as pesticides, while others are used as chemical reagents. In medicine, alkaloids are mainly used because of their potent anticancer activity against various cancers. Moreover, they act rapidly in specific areas of the nervous system (Mohan et al. 2011).

Anthraquinones are abundant in nature and constitute the largest class of natural pigments, consisting of 700 different compounds, and approximately 200 can be isolated from plants. Not only in plants, it can also be found in bacteria, fungi, and some animals.

The bioactivities of anthraquinones include anticancer, anti-inflammatory, diuretic, antifungal, antibacterial, and antimalarial activities (Diaz et al. 2018). This compound can be used to prepare anthrone, a compound commonly used to determine carbohydrate content through colorimetric assays. Meanwhile, a derivative of anthrone is utilized in pharmacies as a laxative. However, the use of this compound is limited because Gorkome et al. (2021) suggested that it is carcinogenic if used in the long term.

Essential oils from *Carica papaya* leaves have potent antimicrobial properties against *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus faecalis*, and *Proteus mirabilia* (Igwe 2015). The major components of essential oils present in plant extracts are benzyl nitrile and beta-nitroethanol (Gao et al., 2010). Fatty acids are complex lipids crucial for metabolic activities. It serves as the “building block” of cell membranes that supply energy, and some derivatives function in cell storage and cell signaling, which are important factors for a cell to survive (De Carvalho & Caramujo, 2018).

Phenols have been associated with degenerative diseases and lower the risk of developing chronic illnesses. Some studies have highlighted its benefits in improving memory and cognitive functions. Flavonoids and Tannins are major classes of phenolic compounds. Flavonoids or bioflavonoids are plant-based compounds that are usually found in vegetables and fruits, such as blueberries and grapes. This component has powerful antioxidant properties and offers various benefits, such as defense of blood vessels, especially for people with diabetes and heart diseases, easing allergies, supporting brain health to avoid dementia, and preventing some cancers. These medicinal properties include antimicrobial, antihistamine, and anti-inflammatory properties. In addition, tannins exhibit health benefits, such as antioxidant, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anti-helminthic, anti-allergic, and antibacterial activities. However, some studies have revealed that it has health consequences such as reduced digestibility, carcinogenic activity, hepatotoxic activity, and promotion of other illnesses; thus, proper consumption is advised (Sharma et al., 2021).

Finally, steroids are used as medical treatments for some illnesses, and they come in two varieties. The most common type of alkaloid is anabolic steroids, which act like male hormones and are also prescribed for patients with late puberty crises. Moreover, steroids can be used to treat patients with cancer or AIDS (acquired immunodeficiency syndrome). Philipkoski (2012).

Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay (Cytotoxicity Assay)

Table 2. Number of alive nauplii in each test tube after 24 hours

Replicates	2000 PPM	1000 PPM	500 PPM	250 PPM	125 PPM	62.5 PPM
A	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	0	0	0	0	1	1
C	0	1	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0
% of death	100	97.5	100	100	97.5	97.5

Table 3. Number of live nauplii in each test tube after 48 hours

Replicates	2000 PPM	1000 PPM	500 PPM	250 PPM	125 PPM	62.5 PPM
A	0	0	0	0	0	0
B	0	0	0	0	0	0
C	0	0	0	0	0	0
D	0	0	0	0	0	0
% of death	100	100	100	100	100	100

Tables 2 and 3 show the number of live, dead, and summary percent mortality in brine shrimp after 24 and 48 h, respectively. The number of survivors and percent mortality were recorded for each dilution. A portable microscope was used to observe and check the condition of the brine shrimp. Based on the observation at 200 PPM, there was no live nauplius, resulting in a 100% mortality rate. At 1000 PPM, one live nauplius was observed, indicating a 97.5% mortality rate. For 500 and 250 PPM, no live nauplii were found, corresponding to a 100% mortality rate. One live nauplius was observed at 125 ppm and 62.5 ppm, one alive nauplius was observed, indicating a 97.5% mortality rate at each concentration. After 48 h, all brine shrimps reached a 100% mortality rate.

Figure 1. Median Lethal Concentration (LC50) of *C. papaya*

Table 4. Median Lethal Concentration (LC50) of *C. papaya*

Concentration (PPM)	Total no. of Brine Shrimp	No. of Dead after 24 hrs	% of Death
2000	40	40	100
1000	40	39	97.5
500	40	40	100
250	40	40	100
125	40	39	97.5
62.5	40	39	97.5

The median lethal concentration (LC50) represents the concentration of a substance that is lethal to 50% of organisms in a toxicity test (Global Seafood Alliance 2019). A substance was considered potent (active) if its LC50 was less than 100 ppm. According to Meyer et al (1982)., a substance is deemed toxic if its LC50 is less than 1000 g/mL, and non-toxic if it exceeds 1000 g/mL. The median lethal concentration (LC50) was determined by probit analysis. Based on the data gathered, the LC50 for the dosage of *C. papaya* after 24 hours was -68977.14 (see Fig. 1), which signifies that the plant extract is toxic.

Allium cepa Test

Table 5. Summary of number of cells in *C. papaya* under 2000 PPM

Mitotic Phases	Number of cells
Prophase	17
Metaphase	6
Anaphase	2
Telophase	3
Total no. of cell in mitosis	28
Non dividing cells	121
Total no. of cells	149

Table 5 shows the distribution of cells across the different stages of mitosis. Of the total number of mitotic cells observed, 17 were in prophase, 6 in metaphase, 2 in anaphase, and 3 in telophase. The most prevalent mitotic stages were those with the highest proportions of cells. In this case, prophase appeared to be the most pervasive stage, followed by metaphase, telophase, and anaphase. There were 121 non-dividing cells in total. The computed mitotic index for the 2000 PPM concentration was 23.14. The mitotic

index is inversely proportional to cytotoxicity. Sub-lethal effects occur when the mitotic index drops below 50% of the negative control, whereas lethal effects are observed when inhibition decreases below 22% (Graña, 2018). Therefore, *C. papaya* extracts have a cytotoxic effect on *A. cepa* root tip cells.

Antibacterial Test (Bioassay)

Table 1. Zone of Inhibition for *E. coli* after 24 hours of incubation

Treatment	Replicates (mm)				Total	Mean
	I	II	III	IV		
Meropenem (+)	31.86	31.42	30.91	29.21	123.4	30.85
95% Ethanol (-)	6.88	9.28	8.43	6.71	31.3	7.83
<i>Carica papaya</i>	15.53	11.39	12.84	17.34	57.10	14.28
Grand mean						17.65

Considerations:

Positive Control (meropenem): Mean ZOI = 30.85 mm, indicating high susceptibility to meropenem.

Negative Control (95% ethanol): Mean ZOI = 7.83 mm, serving as a baseline for no antimicrobial effect.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the antimicrobial effectiveness of the various treatments against *E. coli* was evaluated after 24 h of incubation. The positive control, meropenem, exhibited a mean zone of inhibition of 30.85 mm, indicating a strong antimicrobial activity across all replicates. In contrast, the negative control, 95% ethanol, produced a mean zone of inhibition of only 7.83 mm, suggesting a minimal antibacterial effect and serving as a baseline for comparison.

The crude extract of *Carica papaya* showed a mean zone of inhibition of 14.28 mm. Although this was substantially lower than that of meropenem, it was significantly higher than that of the negative control, indicating that the *Carica papaya* extract possesses notable antimicrobial properties against *E. coli*. The grand mean of all treatments was 17.65 mm, highlighting the overall effectiveness of the tested substances, with *Carica papaya* showing moderate antibacterial activity.

Table 2. Zone of Inhibition for *S. Aureus* after 24 hours of incubation

Treatment	Replicates (mm)			Total	Mean
	I	II	III		
Clyndamycin (+)	19.61	11.30	27.72	58.63	19.54
95% Ethanol (-)	6.88	9.28	8.43	24.59	8.20
<i>Carica papaya</i>	15.53	11.39	12.84	39.76	13.25
Grand mean					13.66

Considerations:

Positive Control (Clyndamycin): Mean ZOI = 30.85 mm, indicating high susceptibility to meropenem.

Negative Control (95% ethanol): Mean ZOI = 7.83 mm, serving as a baseline for no antimicrobial effect.

Based on the data presented in Table 1, the antimicrobial effectiveness of the various treatments against *E. coli* was evaluated after 24 h of incubation. The positive control, meropenem, exhibited a mean zone of inhibition of 30.85 mm, indicating a strong antimicrobial activity across all replicates. In contrast, the negative control, 95% ethanol, produced a mean zone of inhibition of only 7.83 mm, suggesting a minimal antibacterial effect and serving as a baseline for comparison.

The crude extract of *Carica papaya* showed a mean zone of inhibition of 14.28 mm. Based on Hudzicki's (2009) zone diameter Interpretative Standards for *Staphylococcus* species, *Carica papaya* leaf extracts showed intermediate effectiveness with zones of inhibition. While the mean of *the C. papaya* leaf extract was substantially lower than that of meropenem, it was significantly higher than that of the negative control, indicating that the *Carica papaya* extract possesses notable antimicrobial properties against *E. coli*. The grand mean of all treatments was 17.65 mm, highlighting the overall effectiveness of the tested substances, with *Carica papaya* showing moderate antibacterial activity.

The antibacterial property of *Carica papaya* is supported by various studies, including Aruljothi et al. (2014), which revealed that papaya leaves could contain active antimicrobial compounds that may hinder the growth of wound infection-causing pathogens in vitro; Anibijuwon and Udeze (2009) suggested that *C. papaya* has antibacterial properties that can be used as a treatment for gastroenteritis, urethritis, otitis media, and wound infections.

Conclusions

C. papaya leaf extract contains various phytochemicals, including alkaloids, anthraquinones, essential oils, fatty acids, flavonoids, phenols, steroids, and tannins.

However, the plant materials used in this study exhibited significant cytotoxicity. Based on the Brine Shrimp Lethality Assay, cytotoxicity resulted in a 100% mortality rate across all tested concentrations, indicating that the plant material has a strong cytotoxic potential. Additionally, the *Allium cepa* test confirmed the impact of the extract on cell division, further underscoring its cytotoxic nature. Moreover, the Kirby-Bauer Assay indicated notable antibacterial activity, especially against *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. While the effectiveness of the extract was lower than that of standard antibiotics, such as Meropenem and Clindamycin, it still exhibited significant inhibition, suggesting its potential as a natural antimicrobial agent.

In conclusion, this study highlights the therapeutic potential of *Carica papaya* leaf extract owing to its diverse bioactive composition and biological activities, particularly its cytotoxicity and antibacterial action. This positions *C. papaya* leaf extract as a candidate for further development in pharmacological applications, especially as a natural antimicrobial and cytotoxic agent

Recommendations

1. As *C. papaya* shows significant toxicity and cytotoxicity, further study is encouraged in vivo and clinical studies are required to determine the safe dosage of *C. papaya* and evaluate its potential toxic effects in more complex biological systems.
2. Since *C. papaya* shows significant toxicity and cytotoxicity, it is essential to determine the phytochemicals that cause it, so that it can be isolated.
3. As the extract showed significant biological activities, sustainable farming and large-scale cultivation of *C. papaya* should be considered to ensure a stable supply of raw materials for both research and industrial applications.

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